

The Universality and Uniqueness of American, British, and Australian English Found in YouTube Platform

Authors : Desi Rahma Yuni Br.Sinulingga^{1*}, Syahron Lubis²

Affiliations : ^{1,2} Universitas Sumatera Utara, Indonesia

*Correspondence : desirahma99yuni@gmail.com

Abstract : The purpose of this research is to find the universality and uniqueness of American, British, and Australian English. The data for this research are videos found on the YouTube platform focused on American, British, and Australian English content. The method used in the analysis of the data consisted of watching the videos carefully and observing them. It used the guidelines adaptation step designed by Alhamami (2013). The results of this research are: 1. the universality language found in American, British, and Australian English languages are in grammar, sound systems, suprasegmental sounds, and part of speech. 2. The uniqueness of language found in American, British, and Australian English languages are in grammar focused on tenses, sound systems focussed on word stress, suprasegmental sounds focused on pronouncing words/dialects, and vocabulary differences.

Keywords : *Universality and uniqueness language, American, British, Australian English.*

License : This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC-BY)

Copyrights : © 2023 by Authors

1. Introduction

The philosophy of language is a study to investigate the nature and position of language as a human activity as well as the conceptual and theoretical foundations of linguistics. The analytical philosophy of language is a distinctive method for explaining, elaborating, and testing the truth of philosophical expressions (Kaelan, 1998). Then, the definition by Alwasilah (2008) supports this definition. Deciphering and testing the truth is only possible through language because language has a cognitive function, namely, with language, humans explain the propositions they think about, whether they are true or false so that they accept or reject them rationally (Alwasilah, 2008). From the definition above, it can be said that the Philosophy of science and language is a study that can tell the truth through language or philosophical expression.

The function of language is as a tool of communication for human beings. Language is the system of communication in speech and writing that is used by people of a particular country and the way of expressing ideas and feelings using movement, symbol, and sound (Hornby: 2000). People acquire language in the same way. It makes the language universal. Besides being universal, language is also unique. It means each language is specific.

In the sense of interlanguage, the universal language is an auxiliary language for international communication, i.e. a language that enables people who do not share their mother tongue to engage in everyday communication (Lehmann: 2003). Language is universal because it has certain things in common: all languages have grammar, sound systems, suprasegmental sounds, parts of speech, etc. Then, language is unique, it will be bound up with the thinking and culture of some people and will be relatively remote from the thinking and culture of other peoples (Lehmann:2003). It is unique because some languages are in spoken form only, not written form. Then, the differences in word formation, grammar, and dialect. In English, there are some differences in dialects: American, British, and Australian.

Even if dialects come from the same source, like American, British, and Australian English, there are differences. They are different, such as in vocabulary, lexis, spelling, pronunciation, grammatical pattern, and so on. But this research will only focus on analyzing the different spelling between them.

YouTube is a social media platform that shares online videos. Many kinds of videos that people can access: social life, food, and drink, education, beauty and mode, pranks, cooking, etc. Currently, YouTube has become one of the most popular platforms for many ages. Many researchers analyze videos on YouTube: analyzing the language used, word formation process, style of language, and so on. It is because we can easily access it, and we can easily find much information that we want. It is a unifier of people in words. The data in this research are videos found on YouTube platforms focused on American, British, and Australian English content. The purpose of this research is to find the universality and uniqueness of American, British, and Australian English.

A similar study was done by Barata (2020) "American English and British English: Vocabulary and Grammar Differences". In his research, he focused on the differences in grammatical aspects such as tenses, prepositions, subject-verb agreement, articles, and some vocabulary differences. The difference between his research and this research is the subject analysis. This research will not just analyze American and British English, but also Australian English. Also, this research does not analyze the differences in grammar and

vocabulary, but analyses the universality and uniqueness between American, British, and Australian.

2. Method

This study used the observation method. The analysis will consist of watching the videos carefully and observing them. The guidelines step is designed by Alhamami (2013). Watching videos and observing them " allows the researcher to analyze language use in greater depth" (Mackey & Gass, 2005). This is a structured observation where pre-specified categories help the observer to gather more objective data about the language lesson (Mackey & Gass, 2005, Wallace, 1998). The purpose of that research was to analyze how teachers explain grammar, while this research's purpose is to analyze the universality and uniqueness between Americans, British, and Australian. Then, this research will be adapting the guidelines by adding specific questions regarding the universality and uniqueness of the English language. It can be said, the evaluation guidelines will consist of questions that analyze the YouTube videos still in the field of language, but will be specified in the field of universality and uniqueness of language.

3. Findings and Discussion

3.1. Finding

3.1.1. *The universality of language*

Universality means all languages have certain things in common. The researcher will analyze some factors that indicate the universality of language:

a. All languages have grammar

Every language has grammar. No matter if it is in different dialects, like American, British, and Australian, even if they have differences in how to put the words together, they are still the same in grammar. No matter whether it is spoken or written. And no matter if it is a first language or a second language. All languages have a system for forming words, a way of organizing words into sentences, and a systematic way of assigning meanings.

b. All languages have a sound system

When we talk about sound systems, we talk about phonology. Phonology is the study of sound. How human beings produce speech sounds. The sound system involves the actual pronunciation of words. American, British, and Australian English dialects have sound systems, even different in pronouncing the words/dialects.

c. All languages have suprasegmental sound

Suprasegmental is beyond the segment (level). It is a prosodic feature in phonetics. Some features such as syllables, pause, length, stress, intonation, pitch, etc. In spoken language, some consonants and vowels combine become syllables. Syllables combine become words and utterances. An utterance is like a unit expression. If we compare segments to each other, then we will get the suprasegmental feature. Such as stress, is a result of the exaggerated pitch, it can make the low pitch lower and the high pitch higher. American, British, and Australian English dialects have suprasegmental sounds, even though there will be differences in some aspects such as stress, intonation, etc.

d. All languages have parts of speech (nouns, verbs, adjectives, prepositions, etc)

All languages have parts of speech, such as nouns to indicate people, things, etc. Verbs indicate the action that the nouns do. Adjectives indicate the quality or state of being of nouns. And prepositions to indicate relationships between other words in a sentence.

3.1.2. *The uniqueness of language*

Besides, language being universal, language is also unique because it is specific. Even though all languages have grammar, sound systems, suprasegmental sound, and parts of speech, and even if they come from the same source, like American, British, and Australian English, still, there are differences between them. Below are the explanations for it:

a. Grammar differences between American, British, and Australian English

This section focused on some tenses that cause differences between those dialects. The table below will show the differences:

Table 3.1.2.1. Grammar differences focussed on tenses

No.	Tenses	American	British	Australian
1.	Present perfect Note: American English uses the present perfect less and past simple more	She <u>ate</u> too much chocolate.	She <u>has eaten</u> too much chocolate.	She <u>has eaten</u> too much chocolate.
2.	- Past simple (dream) Note: American English's verb ending in +ed, British's verb ending in 't', it also happens in past participle	I <u>dreamed</u> about you last night.	I <u>dreamt</u> about you last night.	I <u>dreamt</u> about you last night.
	- Past participle (smell) Note: "t" is much more common in British and Australian English, while in American English people commonly use +ed	I <u>smelled</u> something weird.	I <u>smelt</u> something weird.	I <u>smelt</u> something weird.

Source: *Love English with Leila and Sabrah Youtube channel, and E2Language Blog website*

b. Sound system differences between American, British, and Australian English

This section focus on how those dialects pronounce or accent the words. The table below will show the differences:

Table 3.1.2.2. The sound system focussed on pronouncing/dialect of the words

No.	Words	American	British	Australian
1.	Harry potter	Harry potter /'pɑ:.tə/	Harry potteh /'pɒt.ər/ (in British the -er is more sound like -eh)	Harry poddah Break down into sound [POT] + [UH] (For Australian English, it is more sound like D-fied, like wadda in water)
2.	Tuesday	Tuesday /'tu:z.deɪ/	Chew-sday /'tʃu:z.deɪ/	Chew-sday /'tʃu:z.deɪ/
3.	Banana	Banana /bə'næn.ə/	Banana /bə'nɑ:.nə/	Banana /bə'nɑ:.nə/
4.	Tomato	Tomato /tə'meɪ.təʊ/	Tomato /tə'mɑ:.təʊ/	Tomato /tə'mɑ:.təʊ/
5.	Water	Water /'wɑ:.tə/	Water /'wɔ:.tər/	Water /'wɔ:.tər/
6.	Coffee	Coffee /'kɑ:.fi/	Coffee /'kɒf.i/	Coffee /'kɒf.i/
7.	Dog	Dog /dɑ:g/	Dog /dɒg/	Dog /dɒg/
8.	Shark	Shark /ʃɑ:rk/	Shark /ʃɑ:k/	Shark /ʃɑ:k/
9.	Zebra	Zebra /'zi:.brə/	Zebra /'zeb.rə/	Zebra /'zeb.rə/
10.	Vase	Vase /veɪs/	Vase /vɑ:z/	Vase /vɑ:z/
11.	Castle	Castle /'kæ.səl/	Castle /'kɑ:.səl/	Castle /'kɑ:.səl/
12.	Missile	Missile /'mɪs.əl/	Missile /'mɪs.aɪl/	Missile /'mɪs.aɪl/

Source: World Friends and Language of Earth YouTube channel

c. Suprasegmental sound differences between American, British, and Australian English

This section focus on one feature of suprasegmental sound which is stress, how they stress the words, and which letter is stressed in that word. The table below will show the differences: stress is shown in bold and underlined.

Table 3.1.2.3. Suprasegmental sounds focused on the stress of the words

No.	Words	American	British	Australian
1.	Vaccine	<u>Vaccine</u>	<u>Vaccine</u>	<u>Vaccine</u>
2.	Adult	<u>Adult</u>	<u>Adult</u>	<u>Adult</u>
3.	Detail	<u>Detail</u>	<u>Detail</u>	<u>Detail</u>
4.	Ballet	<u>Ballet</u>	<u>Ballet</u>	<u>Ballet</u>
5.	Brochure	<u>Brochure</u>	<u>Brochure</u>	<u>Brochure</u>
6.	About	<u>About</u>	<u>About</u>	<u>About</u>
7.	Because	<u>Because</u>	<u>Because</u>	<u>Because</u>
8.	Different	<u>Different</u>	<u>Different</u>	<u>Different</u>
9.	Water	<u>Water</u>	<u>Water</u>	<u>Water</u>

Source: English Accent Training Youtube channel, and ResponsiveVoice website

d. Vocabularies differences between American, British, and Australian English

Here are some vocabularies differences with the same meaning found between those dialects. The table below will show the differences:

Table 3.1.2.4. Vocabularies differences

No.	Vocabularies			Meaning
	American	British	Australian	
1.	Chips	Crisps	Chips	Keripik
2.	French fries	Chips	(Hot) chips	Kentang goreng
3.	Cookies	Biscuits	Biscuits	Biscuit
4.	Tractor-trailer	Lorry	Truck	Truk
5.	Bangs	Fringe	Fringe	Poni
6.	Candy	Sweets	Lollies	Permen
7.	Swimsuit	Swimming costume	Swimmers	Pakaian renang
8.	Forest	The woods	Forest	Hutan
9.	Apartment	Flat	Apartment	Apartemen
10.	Grocery store	Supermarket	Supermarket	Took serba ada
11.	Comforter	Duvet	Doona	Selimut
12.	Bell peppers	Peppers	Capsicums	Paprika
13.	Rain boots	Wellies	Gumboots	Sepatu but
14.	Flip flops	Flip flops	Thongs	Sandal jepit
15.	Gas station	Petrol station	Petrol station	Pom bensin
16.	Pants	Trousers	Pants	Celana panjang
17.	Sidewalk	Pavement	Footpath	Trotoar
18.	Sneakers	Trainers	Sneakers	Sepatu karet
19.	Movie theater	Cinema	Movies	Bioskop
20.	Cell phone	Mobile phone	Phone	Telepon

Source: English with Lucy and World Friends Youtube channel

3.2. Discussion

The means of the universality of language is that all languages have certain things in common. It makes all languages have similarities to each other. In this case, American, British, and Australian English also have some things the same. They are the same as grammar, sound system, suprasegmental sound, and parts of speech.

Besides being universal, language is also unique. It means languages have specific things that make them different from each other. Even if they come from the same source, they still have differences. In this case, researchers analyze the uniqueness of American, British, and Australian English dialects, which makes them different because they have their uniqueness.

The first difference is in grammar focussed on tenses. Two differences in tenses have been found, in present perfect and past simple tenses, and past participle forms. Second, in sound systems, sound focuses on how those dialects pronounce or accent the words. Two examples have been found, in pronouncing the words Harry Potter and Tuesday. Third, in suprasegmental sound, it focuses on one feature of it, which is stress, how they stress the words, and which letter is stressed in that word. Five examples have been found. They are vaccine, adult, detail, ballet, and brochure. Fourth, in vocabulary differences with the same meaning, 15 examples have been found. One of the examples is the difference in vocabulary. To express *kentang goreng*, Americans will say chips, and also Australians. But, the British will say it crisps.

4. Conclusion

From the findings and discussion, it can be concluded that besides language being universal, language is also unique. Certain things in common make language universal. Some of them that are discussed in this research is that they have grammar, sound systems, suprasegmental sounds, and parts of speech. Then, there is some uniqueness of language that makes them different. Some of them that are discussed in this research are grammar focused on tenses, sound system focused on word stress, suprasegmental sound focused on pronouncing words/dialects, and vocabulary differences.

References

- Alhamami, M. (2013). Observation of YouTube Language Learning Videos (YouTube LLVS). *TEwT: The Journal of Teaching English with Technology*, 3-17.
- Alicia Febriani, F. R. (2019). An Analysis of Language Style in "To All The Boys I've Loved Before" Movie. *JOM FKIP*, 1-12.
- Alwasilah, C. (2008). *Filsafat Bahasa dan Pendidikan*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Barata, P. T. (2020). American English and British English: Vocabulary and Grammar Differences. *JLIC: Journal of Language Intelligence and Culture*, 101-114.
- Dirgeyasa, I. W. (2015). Reviewing the British English (BRE) and American English (AME) Dialects. *Language Circle: Journal of Language and Literature*, 105-118.
- Hornby, A. S. (2000). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kaelan. (1998). *Filsafat Bahasa: Masalah dan Perkembangannya*. Paradigma.

- Lehmann, C. (2003). *On the idea of a universal language*. In C. Lehmann, *Linguistic cultural identity and international communication* (pp. 111-124). Saarbrücken: AQ-Verlag.
- Sunardi. (2011). Filsafat Analisis Bahasa dan Hubungannya dengan Ilmu Linguistik Pragmatik. *LITE: Jurnal Bahasa, Sastra, dan Budaya*, 64-83.